

Imperial Acceptance: Chechens in the Discourse of Russia's Pro-Regime Nationalist Hardliners

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Introduction

Why do pro-regime nationalist hardliners in Putin's Russia exhibit both admiration and hostility toward the Chechens? What explains this ambivalent attitude toward them—and, arguably, toward other ethnic minorities? Russia's re-invasion of Ukraine in 2022 sent shockwaves throughout the country, including the deterioration of xenophobic and nationalist sentiments, as documented in numerous reports (Goble 2025, Yudina 2024, Umarov 2024). While hatred toward immigrants and various indigenous populations has generally surged, Chechens as a particularly visible ethnic minority have been at the forefront of this process.

In this paper, we define as nationalist hardliners loosely organized or semi-autonomous actors in the on-line and off-line worlds who, although loyal and broadly aligned with nationalist goals of Putin's regime, may also criticize it for perceived weakness, inaction, or insufficient aggression. They advocate for uncompromising policies against perceived internal and external enemies and try to persuade the regime toward greater repression and violence, promoting discourses of national, cultural, or imperial superiority, and hostility toward migrants or ethnic minorities (Laryš 2025).

Owing to the potent personal bonds of president Vladimir Putin with Chechnya's strongman Ramzan Kadyrov, and Chechnya's special place in the hierarchy of federal politics, pro-Moscow regime's infamous Chechen fighters deployed on the Ukraine battlefields have been regarded as both alien, loyal, committed, and untrustworthy. Appreciated, feared, and cursed at the same time, Chechen fighters have been a topic of heated debates in the midst of Russia's pro-regime and pro-war nationalist hardliners who have come to exhibit a complex attitude toward this Muslim North Caucasian ethnic community long seen as troublesome and dangerous.

Diving into a nuanced empirical analysis of these online platform debates, we introduce the term *imperial acceptance* to describe this multifaceted attitude in that, as we claim, Russian

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pro-regime hardliners legitimize their generally favorable and condescending attitude toward the Chechens in terms of the latter's contribution to the wartime effort of their imperial domain. At the core of imperial acceptance lies an assumption that notwithstanding the Chechens' cultural, religious, and racial differences, or rather the latter group's inferiority vis-à-vis the Russians, and the troubled history of Russo-Chechen relations, pro-Moscow Chechens' contribution to Russia's war efforts on the ground in Ukraine and common enemies pave the ground for their conditional acceptance by Russian nationalists.

As we demonstrate in our article, for Russian nationalists, imperial acceptance is in essence condescending, giving a racially and culturally inferior group an opportunity to enter a superior civilizational realm of *russkiy mir* (Russian world). Pro-Moscow Chechens' military prowess, coupled with their perceived willingness to fight and die for the sake of their imperial domain, demonstration of traditional values and xenophobic attitudes to the outside world are thus seen by Russian nationalist hardliners as a turning point for these North Caucasian Muslim groups for their structural rehabilitation.

There is a number of reasons why this topic is important and timely. First, the Kremlin has relied on the backing of nationalist hardliners and Z-bloggers to rally popular support for its military efforts in Ukraine and recruit soldiers since the re-invasion of Ukraine (Laryš 2025; Jensen and Howard 2023, Kruglova 2023). The standing of nationalist hardliners has strengthened since 2022, with the public display of xenophobic, nationalist and racist sentiments becoming more socially acceptable, among other things. It is crucial for the Kremlin to maintain the support of these hardline groups and there have been reports that Russian authorities have been put under pressure to balance their military efforts and social policies with the risen expectations of the hardliners (Wollast et al. 2024, Fediunin 2023, Sultanalieva 2025).

Second, and relatedly, maintaining the support of nationalist hardliners needs to be balanced off with maintaining the sympathies of Russia's ethnic minorities, of which the Chechens are a visible, disciplined, and well-organized part owing to the existence of paramilitary-styled Chechen armed force de facto placed under Kadyrov's personal command. The pacification of Chechnya in the early 2000s was considered Putin's primary success that helped him take grip on the Kremlin cabinets. Putin's personal bond with Ramzan Kadyrov (Souleimanov 2014; Hughes and Sasse 2016; Russell 2008), has shaped federal politics since the mid-2000s.

Chechnya – and Chechens – have thus been seen as a litmus test for the stability of Putin's regime. Chechnya's role within Russia is in a broader sense a symbol of Moscow's ability to maintain control over the volatile Muslim-majority North Caucasus, once the hotbed

of violent Salafi-jihadist insurgency and terrorism. A deterioration of relations between Moscow and Grozny might pose a threat to Russia's territorial integrity, as it would expose the underlying ethnic and nationalist tensions that have simmered beneath the surface since the collapse of the Soviet Union. This makes the topic of Russian nationalist hardliners' interaction with Chechens a particularly pressing topic to study.

From here on, this paper proceeds as follows. In the following chapter, the historical stage of complex Russo-Chechen relations is set. Making sense of the images and perceptions of the Chechens drawing on the two centuries of peaceful and armed encounters between Russian colonizers and Chechen highlanders are essential for understanding the ongoing debates that often refer to the former. Then, we introduce in detail the concept of imperial acceptance – the central argument of our paper. Following a chapter on methods and data collection, we offer an empirical analysis based on primary data from hardliners' social media channels. In the concluding remarks, we sum up our empirical findings and point to the prospects of a conflict between Russian hardliners and Chechens getting out of control.

The Image of the Chechens in the Russian Society

Long before the Chechen wars of the 1990s, Chechens – and North Caucasian highlanders, *gortsy*, in general - had already occupied an important place in the Russian popular imagination as violent and dangerous. The stereotype of the "wicked Chechen who whets his dagger keen" dates back to Tsarist times. As the most populous North Caucasian ethnic group, Chechens were often viewed by both Russians and neighboring mountain peoples as particularly aggressive and fiercely resistant to Russian rule. The figure of the *abrek*—a lone, armed honorable outlaw defying imperial authority and driven by righteous vendetta—became a key symbol of this image. By the Soviet era, following Chechen resistance to Bolshevik rule, collectivization, and alleged collaboration with Nazi forces, the *abrek* evolved into a vilified figure—an “enemy of the state” (Russell 2005).

Nineteenth-century works such as Tolstoy's *Hadji Murat* and Pushkin's *Prisoner of the Caucasus* imparted a sometimes admiring, sometimes horrified picture of the Chechen as a fierce primitive, an archetypical noble savage, who would never shirk from a fight, an impression only solidified during the numerous Chechen rebellions that accompanied the gradual Russian colonization of the region since the late 18th century. As a result, there is a general assumption that banditry and resistance are deeply ingrained within the Chechen national identity (Souleimanov 2007; Galeotti 2017).

In the 1990s, even prior to the outbreak of war, Chechen criminal networks became a powerful force within the wider Russian underworld, albeit neither as omnipotent nor as omnipresent as suggested in the Russian criminal imaginary. As these gangs rose in influence, public and official perceptions of Chechens shifted from romanticized outlaws to *bandity* (bandits). Among organized crime groups of the time, the Chechen mafia was considered particularly successful, marked by its use of extreme violence and tight-knit organization. In terms of reputation, Chechens draw on a combination of clannish social organization, a culture of banditry and vendetta, and a fierce sense of loyalty to their ethnic kin rather than to country. The Chechen networks, including the criminal ones, have been more cohesive than their Russian counterparts (Russell 2005; Galeotti 2017).

The First Chechen War in 1994–1996 significantly shaped nationalist sentiments of the Russian society. In Moscow, police began systematically targeting individuals who appeared to be from the Caucasus—checking documents and permits in what amounted to a campaign of ethnic profiling (Wales 2016). Under Dzhokhar Dudayev, Chechnya became a criminal fiefdom. The efficiency and ruthlessness of the Chechens has given them a powerful ‘brand name’ (Galeotti 2017). Public attitudes against Chechens hardened further in 1999 following a series of apartment bombings in Moscow and other cities. Regardless of ongoing theories implicating Russian security services, popular opinion overwhelmingly blamed Chechens, transforming their image from noble savages to sinister threats (Russell 2005; Kolsto & Blakkisrud 2016).

Meanwhile, growing hostility extended beyond Chechens to other peoples of the Caucasus, whom many Russians could not distinguish from one another. Despite their relatively light skin tone, Caucasians have been frequently subjected to racial slurs such as *chernye* (“blacks”) or *chernozhopyie* (“black-arsed”). Law enforcement coined the euphemistic yet discriminatory label “person of Caucasian nationality” (*litso kavkazskoi natsional’nosti*). The anti-Chechen sentiment that intensified after the 1999 apartment building bombings, the 9/11 attacks, the 2002 Moscow theatre siege and Beslan in September 2004 was further exacerbated by ongoing domestic terrorism. The resulting Caucasophobia spread rapidly and pervasively among the Russian population (Russell 2005; Yudina 2015).

The anti-Caucasian and anti-Chechen prejudices permeated the cultural sphere as well. For instances, in the popular film *Brat* (1997), a Russian protagonist delivers the infamous line, “You’re not my brother, you black-assed scumbag” (*‘Ne brat ty mne, gnida chernozhopaya’*). Daily racism—particularly at the hands of law enforcement—has remained pervasive, manifesting in ethnic profiling, street harassment, and routine police abuse. Against this background, Chechens were usually grouped with immigrants from the Caucasus in general, with a more

articulate reputation for being violent, fierce, and vindictive (Open Society Institute 2006; 2018, Smirnov 2007).

These sentiments have been grounded in deeper cultural and religious hostilities (Kolstø 2014). Three dominant stereotypes emerged in portraying Caucasians as the Other: (1) uncivilized and ill-mannered, (2) culturally alien and backward, and (3) parasitic on state resources. Many Russians viewed the federal subsidies to Chechnya after the main phase of the Second Chechen War and the installation of the puppet leader Akhmat Kadyrov in 2000 as bribes to local warlords intended to prevent renewed violence (Blackburn 2021). In the early 2000s and 2010s, during a period marked by heightened Caucasophobia and nationalist slogans such as “Stop feeding the Caucasus,” individuals from the Caucasus—particularly Chechens—were the primary targets of negative public sentiment and economic grievances over disproportionate state subsidies to the North Caucasus. In contrast, people from Central Asia elicited less frequent hostility at the time (VTsIOM 2010; Kolstø 2014).

A large part of the Russian population has also been concerned that Ramzan Kadyrov treats Chechnya as his personal fiefdom, where Russian laws do not apply, and that Chechnya has become more independent in practice than at any time since it was conquered under the tsars. What is more, Russians are paying for it, as 80% of Chechnya’s budget comes from subsidies from Moscow. In addition, much of the money has been spent on Kadyrov’s luxurious lifestyle and extravagant vanity projects, such as the construction of a shiny commercial center that no one visits and a huge mosque dedicated to Akhmad Kadyrov (Galeotti 2017).

With the invasion of Ukraine in 2014, the main target of societal hatred, endorsed by state propaganda, shifted from Caucasians to Ukraine and the West — or, more precisely, there was an escalation of hate rhetoric toward the West, which had already been present in propaganda before 2014. Kadyrov became a vocal supporter of the war against Ukraine and the West as a pro-regime actor, which in turn tempered the public anti-Caucasus and anti-Chechen discourse of pro-regime hardline nationalists. More recently, although the overall structure of xenophobia and racism in Russia has remained relatively stable, the intensity of negative attitudes toward Caucasians has declined. According to a Levada Center survey from January 2022, tolerant attitudes toward Chechens increased from 9% to 22%, while negative perceptions dropped from 57% to 41% (Levada Tsentr 2022).

In the most recent opinion polls from 2024–2025, the highest levels of social distance were recorded toward migrants from Central Asia and the lowest levels of social distance were expressed toward Chechens. These shifts in public perception have occurred against the back-

drop of major geopolitical and social developments—including the re-invasion of Ukraine, escalating tensions with the West, and high-profile incidents involving migrants. Notably, a significant rise in positive attitudes toward Chechens was recorded in 2022—likely linked to their prominent role in Russia’s “special military operation” (Levada Tsentr 2024; 2025; HRW Livestream 2025). This indicates that negative and xenophobic attitudes in Russia toward various ethnic groups are highly context-dependent. The collective memory of the Chechen wars and terrorist attacks associated with Chechens appears to be gradually fading, creating space for newer resentments directed at other ethnic or otherwise defined minorities.

Introducing the Concept of Imperial Acceptance

According to Aleksandr Verkhovskiy, prominent expert on Russian nationalist, pro-regime nationalist vigilante groups such as Northern Man (*Severnyi chelovek*) or the more prominent Russian Community (*Russkaya obshchina*) no longer target Chechens or people from the North Caucasus. This is because their hostility is primarily directed toward migrants, whereas Chechens, despite persisting stereotypes and prejudices, are not classified as such (Interview Verkhovskiy 2025). Pro-regime hardliners look at Chechens through the optics of Russian imperialism. In Russia’s imagination, imposing its language, culture, and authority on non-Russian populations is framed as an act of generosity, bestowing “superior” culture, greatness, and modernity (Riabchuk 2016; Kassymbekova and Marat 2022).

Such an imperial supremacist view echoes 19th-century European colonialism, with Putin using rhetoric reminiscent of colonialist “civilizing missions” to justify the domination and exploitation of other nations, claiming they were reluctantly undertaking the burden that white men had to bear to defend against barbarians and savages (Suny 2022). Pro-regime nationalists see Russians as bringers of light and civilization to the non-Russian nations that are keeping and ‘primitive’ customs such as blood revenge typical for ‘backward tribes’ and only with ‘the conquest of the Caucasus by the Russian Empire that law and order arrived there’ (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 10 October 2024). Sons of Monarchy posted that:

“Russians are improving the quality of life for all the other indigenous peoples of our country. [...] Compare the bandit hole that Chechnya was during its years of independence with the prosperous and peaceful region it is today” (Syny monarkhii, 17 July 2023).

Although officials within Putin’s regime are aligned rather with an archaic imperial nationalist statism and chauvinism, official discourses have recently shown a slightly greater openness toward Russian ethnic nationalism based on xenophobic prejudices toward Caucasians, Muslims, and immigrants than in the past. However, it still does not constitute an element of state policy or propaganda. Among the senior regime officials, Aleksandr Bastrykin, head of the Investigative Committee (*Sledstvennyi komitet, SK*) since 2011, appears to be the only figure who publicly endorses Russian ethnic nationalism and denigrates immigrants (Interview Verkhovskiy, 2025).

These ethnic, racial, and xenophobic prejudices are also shared by pro-regime hardline nationalists, which may create rifts not only between them and Kadyrov’s regime in Chechnya but also between them and Putin’s regime itself. In this context, nationalist hardliners often describe the authorities as “accomplices of the Caucasus and Islam in the fight against the Russian people” (Pain 2015)—a label even used by loyalists. These xenophobic sentiments have long been fueled primarily by forces opposed to the regime. Therefore, any actions against Chechens—even from loyal nationalists—may be perceived rather sensitively by the authorities. Against the backdrop of generally changed patterns of hostility toward particular nations — in which Chechens have come to be viewed more favorably since the re-invasion of Ukraine at the expense of migrants and other groups — this shift is also reflected by hardline nationalists in what we coined as imperial acceptance.

Imperial Acceptance

This article introduces the concept of imperial acceptance—a belief among pro-regime nationalist hardliners that the ‘usefulness’ of Russia’s ethnic minorities should be evaluated according to their contribution to the preservation and expansion of the Russian statehood. For these actors, the state and empire possess a sacred value, standing above the interests of individual citizens (Blackburn 2021; Pain 2016). Consequently, the worth of any ethnic group is assessed through its perceived service to the unity and strength of the Russian state. Within this worldview, all inhabitants of Russia are expected to subordinate their particularistic interests to the broader goal of national interests, however they might be defined by pro-regime hardliners

Ethnic minorities and their members are therefore conditionally accepted or rejected based on how effectively they are believed to advance Russian imperial objectives. within the broader patterns of ethnic discrimination in Russia’s daily life, such as job market (Bessudnov and Shcherbak 2020). Whenever pro-regime hardliners perceive that a group—or any element

of its behavior, cultural memory, or identity—conflicts with the state’s imperial interests, their latent xenophobia, racism, and hostility rapidly surface and imperial acceptance is revoked. Historical “sins” are recalled, accusations of foreignness and disloyalty are revived, and the alleged harm these groups have inflicted upon the Russian state is publicly condemned:

“By trying to confront Prigozhin through public statements, they [Kadyrov’s closes associates] only reinforce the perception of discord among the Russian elites, the piling up of internal contradictions, and the persistent expectation of a civil war — especially given the biographies of Delimkhanov and Daudov [Kadyrov’s associates fighting against Russia in the First Chechen War]” (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 1 June 2023).

Such perceived transgressions must be punished or “corrected” before these minorities can regain legitimacy and “earn” imperial acceptance—that is, the right to feel part of the empire, or, as one post puts it, to “become a person completely Russian in spirit” (Syny monarkhii, 19 September 2025). Ethnic groups historically subjugated by Russia—including the Chechens—are not expected to become ethnic Russians (Severnii chelovek, 16 December 2023). Rather, they are to integrate into the broader Russian political and civilizational project (Kolesnikov 2023).

In this framework, participation in warfare constitutes the ultimate demonstration of loyalty. Fighting alongside Russians in Ukraine is framed as the highest expression of faithfulness to the empire. As we show drawing on empirical data, this inclusion, however, is profoundly conditional: ethnic and religious diversity in a Russia’s supranational unity is tolerated only insofar as it serves the geopolitical and imperialist ambitions of the Russian state. Those who fight are symbolically incorporated into the national community; those who do not—particularly migrants—are portrayed as threats to social order (Espanola, 17 December 2024). Military service thus functions simultaneously as a test of loyalty and a mechanism of imperial consolidation. This logic is exemplified in the rhetoric of the *Syny monarkhii* channel:

"The best path for Russia’s indigenous Muslims is to integrate as much as possible into the Russian world, befriend Russian Christians, and jointly resist both the godless West and the migration- and Wahhabi-driven pressure from the south [...] In the Russian Empire, your ancestors could achieve a lot if they faithfully served Russia. In a global Islamic Caliphate, you’ll only be lackeys" (Syny monarkhii, 2 September 2023).

and

"Let's distinguish between indigenous and non-indigenous Muslims in Russia. The creeping occupation by migrants from Central Asia and the [south] Caucasus—lobbied for by corrupt officials—is just as much a threat to Russia as the war with NATO in Ukraine. Let's distinguish between indigenous Russian Muslims—from Chechnya, Dagestan, Tatarstan, and Bashkortostan—who fight side by side with Russians for the Russian world, and incoming Islamo-fascists who take over our cities and form criminal groups while our men are at the front"(Syny monarchii, 15 July 2023).

A clear hierarchy emerges in this discourse. Ethnic groups are valued according to their degree of utility to the regime and imperial state. Chechens—once demonized as separatist and jihadist enemies—are now described as conditionally loyal allies because of their integration into the state's coercive apparatus, their role in suppressing Salafism (often labeled "Wahhabism"), and Kadyrov's regime promotion of 'traditional values.' Yet this inclusion remains deeply paternalistic: ethnic minorities are accepted only under the tutelage of ethnic Russian authority (Severnyi chelovek, 16 December 2023).

Compared to Chechens and other 'native' Muslim groups, migrants are less likely to be accepted by pro-regime hardliners. They are consistently portrayed as inferior and socially dangerous. Migrants, mostly from Central Asia, are contrasted unfavorably with "native" Muslims and reproached for their alleged unwillingness to participate in the war. Nationalist hardline commentators frequently assert that few, if any, Central Asian migrants fight on Russia's side in Ukraine—interpreting this absence as proof of their disloyalty and lack of civic consciousness (Interview Verkhovskiy, 2025). Because migrants are typically non-citizens, they are assumed to lack a "sense of duty" toward the imperial state, rendering their loyalty and contribution suspect.

In the case of the Chechens, their acceptance depends on the behavior of its individuals, its elites—especially Ramzan Kadyrov—and their perceived alignment with imperial interests. Imperial acceptance can be granted or withdrawn by hardliners depending on whether Chechens' actions are seen as reinforcing or undermining Russian statehood. Kadyrov is praised by pro-regime nationalists for his suppression of radical Islamism and separatism, viewed as contributions to the consolidation of Russian authority in the North Caucasus (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 26 July 2024). He is also revered for his support of "traditional values," pro-regime jingoism, and

virulent rhetoric against common enemies such as Ukrainians and the West (Radio Svoboda, 2025). Kadyrov’s tirades are exemplified by his statement:

“I give you my word that we will destroy everyone. We will not take these *shaytans* prisoner, but will burn them. We will stop nowhere. Our territory is not only Zaporizhzhia or Kherson, but also Odesa, Kyiv, Kharkiv. And all of Ukraine — that is our Russian territory” (Masyuk 2022).

At the same time, as discussed later in this paper, Kadyrov supposedly undermines the unity of the imperial state through other actions and policies. Pro-regime hardliners openly criticize Kadyrov for anything they perceive as detrimental to the unity of the Russian state—such as the behavior of his units on the front line, his lavish lifestyle financed by the Russian budget, or his protection of Chechens within Russia from prosecution for crimes they have committed.

Consequently, pro-regime nationalist hardliners display a degree of ambiguity in their attitudes toward Chechens, whom they view as both alien and dangerous, yet simultaneously as fellow fighters in the defense of the motherland and the empire. Chechens have a reputation among hardliners as tough fighters active on the Ukrainian battlefields, as well as conservative, masculine, and archaic—all traits aligned with the current patriarchal and conservative model advanced by the regime and its ideologues, which is presented as the ideal direction for Russia (Kolesnikov 2023).

The inherent tension in relations between nationalist hardliners and Chechens, expressed through the notion of imperial acceptance, arguably serves as a litmus test for the stability of the regime. While points of friction between Kadyrov and other pro-regime actors already exist, they are able to coexist. Yet this fragile equilibrium could easily shift in the event of a political or military crisis, particularly given that both sides possess weapons and combat experience acquired in Ukraine and in earlier conflicts, including the Chechen wars (Romanovsky 2024).

Data Collection and Methods

Chechens have been chosen as a case study of imperial acceptance because, unlike other minorities, they are institutionalized and supported by a powerful pro-regime actor embedded in a subnational authoritarian regime of Kadyrov’s Chechnya. In addition, the highly charged historical relationship between Chechens and Russia has profoundly influenced the country’s politics, security, society, and culture since the eighteenth century—far more than in the case of

any other ethnic minority in the North Caucasus or elsewhere within the borders of current Russia.

Kadyrov’s subnational dictatorial regime declares loyalty to Moscow and organizes its own combat units. He has successfully integrated himself and his military forces into the war machine and patronage network of Putin’s regime. Kadyrov famously referred to himself as “Putin’s infantry” as early as 2007—a phrase he has repeated many times since (RIA Novosti, 2021). For these reasons, other minorities in Russia—such as the Tatars, Bashkirs, or Kalmyks—arguably do not provoke as much emotion, whether positive or negative, as the Chechens do.

For the discourse analysis of imperial acceptance, we selected nine Telegram channels (see Table 1) administered by pro-war hardliners. Telegram was chosen because of its relevance—over 90 million users as of September 2025—and the relative autonomy it provides from state censorship, unlike platforms directly controlled by the Russian government such as VKontakte or Odnoklassniki (Lekander, 2025). We selected prominent pro-war hardliners with large followings (tens of thousands of subscribers) for their influence among pro-regime nationalists and their frequent focus on topics related to Chechens and Kadyrov.

The key selection criterion was not simply audience size but representativeness—capturing a variety of pro-regime hardliners with the potential to influence this pro-war and pro-regime hardline nationalist community estimated by various sources to be around 10–15% of the Russian population (Kappinen and Zhuravlev 2023; Loginova 2024; RBK 2023). The main goal of the selection process was to include a representative sample of the most popular hardline nationalist bloggers and influencers—currently the only actors in Russia with limited autonomy to discuss political topics, the war, and related issues within a relatively pluralistic pro-war and loyalist discursive habitat.

Table 1. Selected Telegram channels and the number of followers

<i>TG channels</i>	<i>15 September 2023</i>	<i>15 September 2024</i>	<i>15 September 2025</i>
Zapiski veterana (Veteran’s Notes)	303,952	359,658	316,248
Española (Voyennaya organitsaziya “Espanola)	40,319	102,268	120,690
“Severnyi chelovek”. Vserossiyskiy (Northern Man)	78,642	133,590	132,009
Obyknovennyi tsarizm (Ordinary Tsarism)	33,767	37,782	40,785
Pozdnyakov 3.0	419,856	668,788	765,173
Trinadtsatyi (Thirteenth)	206,661	307,521	
Syny monarkhii (Sons of Monarchy)	43,151	71,397	86,062
DShRG Rusich	129,276	235,103	247,324
Russkaya obshchina ZOV (Russian Community)	130,071	608,095	669,677

The range of actors within the hardline nationalist milieu illustrates the heterogeneity of pro-regime forces. Individual influencers selected for this study include Aleksei Kargapoltsev, allegedly residing in Belgorod, who operates the online platform *Veteran's Notes* (*Zapiski veterana*), and Yegor Guzenko, who runs the Telegram channel *Trinadtsatyi* (Fokus, 2023). Other channels belong to combat units such as *Espanola* and *Rusich*, composed largely of Russian ultra-nationalists, football hooligans, and neo-Nazi elements with a history of violent engagement in Ukraine and beyond.

Loyalist vigilante nationalist movements—both digital and offline—also play a significant role, particularly those represented by *Pozdnyakov*, *Severnyi chelovek* (“Northern Man”), and *Russkaya obshchina* (“Russian Community”). While *Northern Man* and *Russian Community* were once perceived as equally influential, over time the latter has gained prominence, relegating *Northern Man* to a secondary position. Finally, ideological currents, critical of the regime in some aspects, are shaped by channels such as *Syny monarkhii* (“Sons of Monarchy”) and *Obyknovennyi Tsarizm* (“Ordinary Tsarism”), which provide a doctrinal framework blending monarchist nostalgia with Russian imperialist narratives.

These channels share common themes and narratives, yet each emphasizes different aspects. *Syny monarkhii* and *Ordinary Tsarism* reject the idealization of the Soviet period and explicitly blame the Bolsheviks for having fostered Chechen disloyalty toward the state. In contrast, *Espanola* and *Trinadtsatyi* are primarily oriented toward military topics, particularly those concerning the *Akhmat* battalion. Nonetheless, all of these channels evaluate Chechens through the same prism—praising or condemning them according to whether they are perceived as contributing to the Russian state, its unity, and its imperial ambitions, albeit from various ideological angles.

A dataset was compiled from nine Telegram (TG) channels covering the period from February 2022 to October 2025. Approximately fifty posts were selected from each channel, resulting in a total of 450 posts as a representative sample for qualitative analysis. The posts were manually collected and categorized according to their references to Chechens—whether to ordinary individuals, Kadyrov, his entourage, or his military units. This dataset was analyzed through open coding in Atlas.ti to identify recurring patterns, key terms, and thematic elements in references to Chechens—what was praised and what was criticized.

This coding process focused on the main topics that condition the granting of imperial acceptance to Chechens — specifically, the most discussed themes among hardliners considered as potential change-makers capable of either granting or revoking that acceptance, depending on the behavior of the Chechens and Kadyrov’s pro-Moscow regime in Chechnya. The

discursive analysis revealed the primary sources of criticism expressed by pro-regime nationalist hardliners toward the Chechens. Two major, conflicting, and potentially game-changing categories emerged:

- Privileges and double standards reportedly enjoyed by Chechens—both ordinary citizens and Kadyrov’s entourage—that undermine state unity and set a negative example for others expected to (re)join the *Russkiy mir* voluntarily or by coercion, such as Ukrainians.
- Identity-building through historical memory, in which certain Chechen heroes are celebrated for their resistance against Russian imperial rule rather than for their loyalty to it.

Double Standards and Undeserved Privileges Impeding the Imperial State’s Unity

Imperial acceptance among pro-regime nationalists is disrupted by the perceived privileges and double standards that Chechens under Ramzan Kadyrov reportedly enjoy within Putin’s regime. Grave danger to the unity and strength of an imperial state, in the eyes of pro-regime nationalist hardliners, arises when one of its constituent parts—Chechnya in this case—does not follow the laws issued by Moscow, places itself above others, operates according to its own—often unwritten—rules, and effectively stands outside the jurisdiction of the federal government. Chechens are accused of behaving as a privileged caste above the law and of trying to secure special advantages for themselves.

This, in turn, corrodes Russian society and its cohesion, as it fuels resentment of Russians not only toward the Chechens but also toward Putin’s regime that allows this situation to persist. It generates a sense of injustice and lawlessness that inevitably harms the unity and greatness of the imperial state—especially when those who, according to the hierarchy, should implicitly remain subordinate, elevate themselves undeservingly above Russians. The so-called ethnic privileges that the Chechens pursue through power and Kadyrov’s patronage networks, tolerated by Moscow, are undermining the unity of the Russian state. Imperial acceptance, in this sense, means recognizing and submitting to the imperial hierarchy rather than challenging it—as Chechens allegedly often do and are criticized for.

Pro-regime nationalists frequently accuse Russian authorities of failing to uphold the law in Chechnya and allowing these double standards for various reasons. They cite numerous incidents in which Chechen individuals allegedly evaded justice, framing these cases as evi-

dence of a broader systemic failure that undermines the integrity of the Russian state. Nationalist bloggers regularly criticize the Chechen leadership's handling of incidents involving aggressive Chechen youth in Russian cities (Zapiski veterana, 24 May 2024). They denounce Kadyrov's public defense of individuals implicated in criminal activities, particularly when these involve attacks on ethnic Russians. Such actions are portrayed as undermining the rule of law and deepening ethnic divisions within the country (Española, 12 September 2024). This discourse underscores a perceived failure of the state to maintain justice and order, fueling insecurity among ethnic Russians:

“Ramzan Akhmatovich Kadyrov must apologize for the insults, lies, and attempts to use his administrative resources to shield clearly delinquent minors who attacked their peers on ethnic grounds [...] At a time when our entire country is confronting a global external threat, undermining the nation in this way is unacceptable. We are outraged that, within a united and indivisible Russia, a single regional head repeatedly defends individuals involved in criminal cases! Why, if everyone is equal before the law, does someone regularly turn out to be ‘more equal’ than others?! Once again, this current situation has crossed all possible lines and is undermining the country's national security” (Española, 8 December 2024).

Chechen leaders—particularly Kadyrov—are frequently portrayed as operating outside the bounds of Russian law. His actions and statements are seen as provocative, reinforcing a sense of Chechen exceptionalism that challenges the authority of the Russian state. Kadyrov's influence, extending far beyond Chechnya, is depicted as endangering national security and the unity of the Russian Federation (Española, 12 September 2024). Recurring argument is that Kadyrov's behavior undermines Russia's broader imperial project. Hardliners claim that “when Ukrainians see the kind of chaos caused by the Chechens, they want nothing like that in their own country,” thereby discrediting the *Russkiy mir* and Russia's rule over occupied Ukrainian territories (Pozdnyakov, 17 June 2024). Kadyrov and his protégés are accused of actively fomenting interethnic hostility and placing themselves above both other peoples of Russia and the state's laws and constitution (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 22 June 2024). Pozdnyakov complains:

“An absolutely privileged class that considers itself above the law—above everyone, in fact. [...] You might as well enshrine it in the constitution that Chechens are a privileged group to whom the laws of Russia do not apply” (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 17 April 2024).

Hardline bloggers depict Kadyrov as a figure who undermines federal authority and operates with near-total impunity. Instances where Kadyrov has publicly challenged federal officials, for instance Aleksandr Bastrykin, director of the Investigative Committee of Russia, are deeply resented as challenge to the political center. Hardliners claim that these privileges have been institutionalized through a process of “Chechenization,” whereby Chechens are allegedly allowed to operate above the law, creating widespread resentment among other ethnic groups. They accuse Kadyrov’s regime of enjoying extralegal autonomy and privileges that place Chechnya outside federal legal oversight (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 21 May 2023).

This phenomenon is often described as a form of parallel sovereignty, in which the Chechen leadership enforces its own norms and laws with impunity. A commonly cited example is the extrajudicial beating of Nikita Zhuravel in August 2023—accused of burning the Quran—by Adam Kadyrov, Ramzan Kadyrov’s son, while in custody in Grozny, where he was transferred to a pre-trial detention, although he was arrested in Volgograd region. The subsequent public praise from Chechen officials for this act is interpreted as emblematic of this “Chechen exceptionalism” (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 6 December 2024; Severnyi chelovek, 15 October 2023). As Ordinary Tsarism stated:

“The Minister for National Policy of Chechnya calmly, and even with pride, recounts how Ramzan Kadyrov’s son beat Nikita Zhuravel, who was accused of setting fire to the Quran, in a detention facility. What does it mean? It means just one thing: there is an ethnic group in the Russian Federation that places itself above the very laws of the Russian Federation—and does so completely openly and without the slightest shame. Where will this lead? It’s not hard to guess. One only needs to look at the historical experience of the 1990s and early 2000s. Unfortunately, the Russian Federation has learned nothing from it” (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 18 August 2023).

Such behavior, according to nationalist commentators, violates the foundational principle of legal equality and erodes the state’s monopoly over violence and justice—an erosion that may have grave consequences (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 4 July 2023). Kadyrov’s unchecked authority, they argue, has come to symbolize the federal government’s failure to assert control. The Kremlin is also accused of outsourcing politically sensitive Muslim and ethnic affairs to Kadyrov, thereby weakening national integration and undermining the rule of law (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 22 July 2023):” When Kadyrov steps onto the federal stage, he cannot

rely on ethnic Russians. Therefore, he needs a different electoral base. That is why he has become the most prominent and zealous advocate for bringing in Islamized migrants, whom he can rely on as an Islamic leader” (Obyknovenyi tsarizm, 5 December, 2024).

Nationalist commentators further claim that Chechens act with impunity because they are shielded by state protection. These cases are portrayed not as isolated incidents but as symptoms of a broader collapse in ethnic relations and legal accountability. Such portrayals reinforce the stereotype of the “privileged ethnic minority” and application of double standards that disregards Russian norms and laws while ethnic Russians are denied equal treatment. Pozdnyakov frequently criticizes Chechens that although they fight for ‘denazification’ of Ukraine, they prevent Chechen girls to see non-Chechen to ‘keep Chechen race pure’ and behave like Nazis themselves:

“A Chechen woman named Lia studies in Moscow but lives in Chechnya. Her relatives reported that she met a young man who was not Chechen — and that became the reason for her persecution, according to media reports. Let us recall that another Chechen woman, Seda Suleymanova, was also abducted for falling in love with a Russian man. Since her disappearance, there has been no news about Seda. For those who didn’t know: the “denazifiers” from Chechnya strictly observe racial purity and forbid their women from having relationships with men of other nationalities — especially Russians. A Chechen woman with a Russian man is considered an enormous disgrace and can be punished by what they call an “honor killing.” That’s what these “denazifiers” are like)))” (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 16 May 2024a).

And

“And just like in the Third Reich, the “denazifiers” from Chechnya, who strictly uphold racial purity, are trying to prevent such relationships. Whether the Moscow police will bend this time again or not is a rhetorical question” (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 16 May 2024b)

Even though Chechens are celebrated as active participants in the war, they are simultaneously derided as the so-called “TikTok Army.” This criticism also reflects resentment toward their perceived privileged status: Chechens are said to have better equipment, avoid dangerous “meat assaults,” and intimidate conscripts in regions such as Kursk, or wield huge influence, loot

property and extort money in Ukraine's occupied territories (Obyknovennyi tsarizm, 3 November 2022). Moreover, Chechen prisoners of war are allegedly exchanged for a disproportionately large number of Ukrainian POWs. For instance, speculation circulated in June 2022 that Ukrainian medic and war hero Yulia Payevska (Taira) had been exchanged for a high-ranking Chechen prisoner—son of Murad Saidov, a Chechen official in Crimea. Although unconfirmed, this rumor outraged pro-war supporters (Syny monarkhii, 18 June 2022; Novaya Gazeta Evropa 2022).

Identity and Memory - Heroes and Villains in the War of Historical Narratives

Imperial acceptance among pro-regime nationalists is rooted in an imperial identity that venerates historical figures based on their contributions to the Russian state and empire. This identity directly conflicts with Chechen national identity and the commemoration of Chechen national heroes—many of whom actively resisted the Russian Empire. Even among pro-regime Chechens, the celebration of such figures provokes significant hostility from pro-regime nationalists, who overlook the fact that their own icons and symbols of Russian anti-Chechen xenophobia and imperialism, Colonel Yuriy Budanov and General Aleksei Yermolov, are widely reviled by Chechens regardless of political alignment.

Viewed as the mastermind behind 19th-century Russian military expansion in the Caucasus, Yermolov effectively conducted a campaign of total war, aiming to leave the local population with no choice but to submit to Russian rule through brutal and indiscriminate violence against the Chechens—such as the extermination of entire villages and forced deportations (Shafee 2015; Elkner 2002, 203–211). Yermolov is celebrated for his military prowess and depicted as a strong, sometimes ruthless leader who effectively subdued resistance in the region, earning him the title "Lion of the Caucasus" (DShRG Rusich, 4 June 2024; Russkaya obshchina, 4 June 2024).

In 2000, during the Second Chechen War, tank commander Colonel Yury Budanov raped and murdered a teenage Chechen girl, Elsa Kungayeva. These acts led to what became the most high-profile war crimes trial of the second war (Russell 2005). Budanov was sentenced to ten years in prison and immediately became a hero among Russian nationalists. In early 2009, he was released early, to the utter dismay of many Chechens loyal to Moscow (Jansen 2010). Some commentators said his case alienated the Chechen and Russian nations even more than the war itself (Sperling 2003).

In 2011, Budanov was assassinated in Moscow by Yusup Temirkhanov, a Chechen who was subsequently captured by Russian law enforcement and sentenced to 15 years in prison. Temirkhanov died—or was killed—in a Russian prison in 2018. He has since become a Chechen folk hero, with his portraits often seen on the rear windows of cars in Chechnya (Ilyasov 2025). Pro-regime nationalists complain about popularity of Budanov’s killer, especially among those, who can influence Chechen people and Chechen youth. Yegor Guzenko (“Trinadtsatyi”) commented on his Telegram channel:

"A Wahhabi from Russian 'pop-MMA'—Shovkhal Churchaev—posted a picture [...] of his idol: the killer of Russian Hero Colonel Yuri Dmitrievich Budanov. How is this scum still alive and living in Russia? I believe all such 'fighters' should be gathered into one battalion and sent to the front in train cars. They're healthy, physically developed—let them prove their 'fitness' there. Honestly, I'm fucking sick of looking at them—running around in cages like baboons—gaining popularity, and worst of all, among the youth" (Trinadtsatyi, 6 August 2023).

Budanov is frequently described as a hero who demonstrated exceptional bravery during the Chechen wars. Calls to honor figures like Budanov and Yermolov are part of a broader narrative of Russian resilience against perceived threats from Chechen and other non-Russian figures. Some TG channels even imply that Ramzan Kadyrov was behind Budanov’s murder (Obyknovenyi tsarizm, 10 June 2025). The narrative surrounding Budanov serves to reinforce a sense of Russian nationalism that is often juxtaposed against the portrayal of Chechen figures like Imam Shamil and Sheikh Mansur, who are celebrated in Chechen culture for their resistance against Russian imperialism.

There is a clear distinction made between Russian heroes and Chechen national figures, with the latter often portrayed negatively. TG posts of pro-regime nationalists suggest that the glorification of these Chechen heroes contributes to a narrative of victimhood and resistance that is at odds with the Russian national identity. Nationalist hardline bloggers express concern over the glorification of Chechen figures like Sheikh Mansur and Baisangur Benoyevskiy, whom they view as anti-Russian. They argue for a re-evaluation of historical narratives that celebrate these figures, advocating instead for the recognition of those Chechens who fought alongside Russians:

"If the heroes of the North Caucasus will be Shamil, Mansur, and Baisangur Benoyevskiy—then that's a straight road to a new Caucasus war and separatism. Baisangur Benoyevskiy was a Russophobe to the core, driven by one goal—to kill Russians. He was like the Shamil Basayev of his time—a moral and physical freak" (Syny monarchii, 29 October 2023).

Chechen national heroes such as Sheikh Mansur or the military commander Baisangur Benoyevskiy are symbols in memory politics, part of Chechen identity which is, however, in direct contradiction to Russia's imperial identity and statist nationalism. Pozdnyakov posted that:

"In Russia, for some reason, among certain ethnic minorities, the heroes are those who, in one way or another, fought against Russia or the Russian people: Salavat, Sheikh Mansur, Imam Shamil, etc. Meanwhile, real heroes are forgotten. Do you know of any Dagestani or Bashkir heroes who fought in the Great Patriotic War (WWII)? They exist!!! But no one turns them into cult figures! No one knows about them, no one builds monuments to them! Instead, ethnic minorities worship bandits who fought against the Russian Empire or Russia. [...] There are also heroes who fought and remained loyal to Russia!!! For example, Hero of the Russian Federation—Chechen Yamadayev! Have you heard of him??? A true hero and patriot of Russia!!!" (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 1 December 2024).

In October 2023, Ramzan Kadyrov officially announced the formation of a new military battalion named after Sheikh Mansur to be integrated into the Russian Ministry of Defense (Kavkazskiy uzel 2023). The battalion was named after one of the Chechen national heroes fighting against Russian imperialism while battalion with identical name was founded and manned by Chechen fighters on the Ukrainian side in 2014. That enraged pro-regime nationalists as it crossed the lines of the imperial acceptance.

In response to this announcement, Yegor Guzenko (Trinadtsatyi) suggested to create a tank regiment named after Yurii Budanov (Trinadtsatyi, 25 October 2023). Pozdnyakov reacted by proposing to creating a battalion named after Heroes of Russia Yuri Budanov and Eduard Ulman, involved in the extrajudicial killing of Chechen civilians, and that movement of Sheikh Mansur was directed against the Russian Tsar and tsarism in general: "What kind of anti-Russian state are we living in? Can someone explain this to me?" he asks (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 24 October 2023a). Also, he added that:

“Since Sheikh Mansur was a faggot, a Nazi, and a rabid Russophobe, the presence of such a battalion in Ukraine is quite justified. But why the hell did we create a paramilitary formation named after this bastard in Russia as well—that’s a big question for me. Maybe then we should also assemble a Vlasov Battalion in Moscow? Why not” (Pozdnyakov 3.0, 24 October 2023b).

Sons of Monarchy commented that:

“Creating a battalion in Russia named after Sheikh Mansur sounds about the same as creating a battalion named after Shukhevych [commander of Ukrainian Insurgent Army]. I’m not exaggerating—just stating the facts. Sheikh Mansur was known exclusively for one thing: he fanatically fought against Russia and hated Russians. And he didn’t even fight for the freedom of his own land, but for the Turks. [...] It’s no coincidence that Mansur became a cult figure among anti-Russian Ichkerian terrorists. And glorifying figures like Sheikh Mansur is playing with fire—it’s pouring gasoline on the flames of separatism and Russophobia in the national republics” (Syny monarchii, 24 October 2023).

In order to conditionally grant imperial acceptance, pro-regime nationalists call for a shift in the cultural narrative to focus on figures who exemplify loyalty to Russia, suggesting that the current glorification of Chechen heroes contributes to ongoing tensions and anti-Russian separatist sentiments. Hardline nationalists argue for the elevation of figures who fought alongside Russians or who contributed positively to Russian history, such as Artsu Tchemoev, a Chechen general who played a role in capturing the anti-Russian resistance leader Baisangur Benoyevskiy (Syny monarchii, 29 October 2023).

This perspective seeks to reshape Chechen identity in a way that aligns more closely with Russian imperial nationalism, promoting figures who exemplify loyalty to the Russian state rather than those who resisted it. Nationalist hardliners critique the existing glorification of anti-Russian figures, suggesting that this leads to a cycle of resentment. By promoting figures who exemplify collaboration with the pro-regime bloggers advocate for a concerted effort to highlight the contributions of Chechens who served the Russian state and Russian national interests. The goal is to foster a sense of imperial pride in a shared heritage that includes unquestionable loyalty to the Russian state. On the other hand, Chechens challenging Russian imperialist legacy in the Caucasus in the slightest possible way prompts waves of outrage amid hardliners.

In September 2025, a proposal by Kadyrov to rename three settlements in Chechnya's northern flatland areas historically settled by Cossacks sparked outrage among some Russian officials who viewed it as an anti-Russian attempt by local elites to erase the presence of Russian population in the North Caucasus and rewrite history. Most importantly, State Duma Deputy Vladimir Shamanov, a veteran of the Chechen wars, strongly criticized the proposal, calling it an "erasure of historical memory" and highlighting that the Russian-speaking population was expelled from the region. Kadyrov sharply criticized Shamanov, reminding of his alleged war crimes during the Chechen wars and other Chechen officials called him names and challenged him (Caucasian Knot 2025):

“De-Russification and de-Cossackization of Russia. We often express outrage over de-Russification in the Baltics, Central Asia, and Ukraine. However, right under our noses, de-Russification and de-Cossackization are taking place in an entire Russian region. [...] The de-Russification of place names in a particular Russian region is the first step toward Russophobia and separatism” (Syny monarchii, 25 September 2025).

Conclusion

The paper investigates the perplexing and ambivalent attitudes of Russian pro-regime nationalist hardliners toward Chechens, especially in the context of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine starting in 2022. On the one hand, Chechens are perceived as culturally and religiously alien, violent, untrustworthy, racially inferior, and historically contentious with Russians, with a long and bloody history of resistance toward the Russian imperial cause. On the other hand, pro-Moscow Chechen fighters have been increasingly accepted by Russian nationalists due to their military contribution on the ground in Ukraine, vocal promotion of traditional values and harsh rhetoric against common enemies, such as Ukrainians or the West.

To make sense of this perplexing phenomenon, we have introduced the term imperial acceptance. Drawing on the large body of empirical data stemming from Russian nationalist hardliners' Telegram channels, we illustrate how the concept of conditional acceptance is constructed evolving around the notion of utility toward the imperial realm and its “organic” interests. Within a perceived hierarchy of ethnic communities, Chechens – a group considered culturally, and religiously inferior to the majority Russians – are ascribed a higher place contingent on their contribution to Russian state's key war efforts in Ukraine.

In this paper, imperial acceptance is defined as a conditional acceptance of ethnic minorities based on their contributions to the imperial cause of the Russian state and *Russkiy mir*. For pro-regime hardliners, Russia's ethnic minorities must subordinate their particular identities to the imperial project. Ultimate loyalty as demonstrated through selfless military service in the ongoing war in Ukraine is the key criterion for acceptance into the superior realm of *Russkiy mir*. This acceptance is profoundly paternalistic: Chechens and Russia's other "native" Muslims are tolerated only insofar as they serve Russia's imperial interests.

While Chechens are officially celebrated as loyal defenders of the state, nationalists depict them as a privileged group operating above the law, shielded by Kadyrov's personal ties to the Kremlin. This perceived "Chechen exceptionalism" is framed as a profound threat to Russia's unity, legality, and imperial order. By tolerating Kadyrov's autonomy and the extralegal behavior of his subordinates, Moscow is seen as undermining its own authority and fostering resentment among ethnic Russians who perceive a loss of justice and equality. In the nationalist imagination, imperial acceptance depends on obedience to the center and respect for hierarchical subordination—principles allegedly violated by Chechnya's informal special status. Consequently, the "Chechen question" becomes a symbol of the regime's weakness, eroding both the cohesion of Russian society and the ideological coherence of its imperial project.

To cement the notion of imperial acceptance, Russian nationalist hardliners have put emphasis on reshaping historical narratives to further align them with the primacy of Russia's imperial interests. Notoriously, nationalist hardliners have strongly rejected as dangerous symbols of separatism the glorification of the famous line of historical Chechen rebel heroes – from Sheikh Mansur to Baisangur Benoevskiy – who resisted Russian imperial conquest. Conversely, Russian heroes like General Yermolov and Colonel Budanov—figures notorious for brutal campaigns against Chechens in the early 19th and late 20th century, respectively—are celebrated by Russian hardliners as icons of Russian imperial legacy.

This conflicting memory politics embodies the tension between Russian imperial identity as seen by nationalist hardliners and Chechen national identity. The creation of a Russian-controlled Chechen-manned military battalion in 2023 named after Sheikh Mansur, a Chechen anti-imperialist hero, sparked outrage among nationalists and was seen as crossing the boundaries of imperial acceptance. While imperial acceptance might relate to Russia's distinct ethnic communities in general, our case study of Chechens illustrates the essence of this condescending acceptance of a visible Muslim community with a history of troubled relations with the Russian state.

Viewed as clearly subordinate vis-à-vis Russians, the ultimate imperial nation, Chechens are nevertheless conditionally accepted into the superior and dominant realm of *Russkiy mir* based on their loyalty, service, and sacrifice to the Russian imperial cause. Nevertheless, imperial acceptance remains precarious. In the event of political destabilization or weakening of the central regime, the fragile coexistence could unravel, potentially resulting in violent confrontations between Russian nationalists and Chechen armed actors, even those nominally aligned with Moscow.

To sum up, the concept of imperial acceptance captures the complex, pragmatic, and hierarchical inclusion of Chechens within Russia's imperial-nationalist discourse. Chechens are granted conditional acceptance based on their military utility and loyalty despite enduring xenophobia and cultural denigration.

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